

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT HYBRIDS AND FERTIGATION LEVELS ON BENEFIT COST RATIO OF CUCUMBER (*Cucumis sativus* L.) UNDER POLY HOUSE CONDITIONSVedika Sharma¹, Amit Saurabh^{*2}, Ruksana³, Diksha Saini⁴, Himanshi⁵ and Pallvi Sharma⁶^{1,3} Ph D Student, Department of Horticulture, Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, India.² Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, India^{4,5,6} M.Sc. Student, Department of Horticulture, Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, Indiadramitsaurabh@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study was conducted on 'Effect of different hybrids and fertigation levels on benefit cost ratio of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) under poly house conditions' was carried out in the year 2021 at Experimental Research farm Chhapang, Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, District Sirmour, Himachal Pradesh during 2021. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with three replications and 16 treatment combinations. Results revealed that among different treatment combinations, (H₃F₃ Aviva+150kg NPK/ha) was recorded maximum cost price (Rs. 433.52), maximum selling price (Rs. 7961.60), benefit (7528.08) and maximum benefit cost ratio 17.37. Hence treatment combination (H₃F₃ Aviva+150kg NPK/ha) gives maximum benefit due to good quality of fruit and lesser losses of insect pest and disease.

Keywords: Benefit, Cucumber, Maximum, Yield**Introduction**

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) is a warm season vegetable crop. It belongs to family Cucurbitaceae, which includes cucumber, pumpkins, gourds and melons. It comprises of 117 genera and 825 species, Nagamaniet et al. (2019). The cucumber was introduced into China in 100 B.C. and into France in the 9th century (Pal et al. 2020). The fruit is consumed as raw, salad and also used for pickling purpose. It is good source of vitamin B, vitamin C and different minerals like iron, potassium, phosphorous and calcium. It had different medicinal properties like helps in digestion, prevents constipation, jaundice and gives a cooling effect. Essential oil present in seeds of cucumber is helpful for body smoothness and brain development (Bhagwat et al. 2018). The stem is 50-250 cm long, robust, obtusely quinquangular, thickly hispidulous, yellowish green, and robust. Tendrils are 10-30 cm long, strong, patent, peduncled, simple, hispid, yellowish green and inserted beside the leaves. The majority of modern hybrids are gynococious (all female flowers).

Table 1 Different treatment combinations

Treatment combinations	Treatment details
H ₁ F ₀	Reeva with 0 kg NPK/ha
H ₁ F ₁	Reeva with 50 kg NPK/ha
H ₁ F ₂	Reeva with 100 kg NPK/ha
H ₁ F ₃	Reeva with 150 kg NPK/ha
H ₂ F ₀	Adiva with 0 kg NPK/ha
H ₂ F ₁	Adiva with 50 kg NPK/ha
H ₂ F ₂	Adiva with 100 kg NPK/ha
H ₂ F ₃	Adiva with 150 kg NPK/ha
H ₃ F ₀	Aviva with 0 kg NPK/ha
H ₃ F ₁	Aviva with 50 kg NPK/ha
H ₃ F ₂	Aviva with 100 kg NPK/ha
H ₃ F ₃	Aviva with 150 kg NPK/ha
H ₄ F ₀	Amber with 0 kg NPK/ha
H ₄ F ₁	Amber with 50 kg NPK/ha
H ₄ F ₂	Amber with 100 kg NPK/ha
H ₄ F ₃	Amber with 150 kg NPK/ha

Gynococious hybrids are commonly employed because they are more productive and mature earlier. The fruit stalk is significantly longer, stronger and hispid, measuring 2-5 cm in length. Hermaphroditic flowers, i.e. perigynous blooms, produce more spherical fruits than epigynous flowers. Flowers that are staminate, pistillate or hermaphrodite can easily be differentiated visually. Fertigation is defined as the combination of irrigation and fertilization which is an important component in production technology in vegetables. Fertigation management controls the qualitative and quantitative attributes of a crop. It is ideal for providing the optimum level of nutrients. The nutrient is supplied near the root zone of plant by the application of water soluble fertilizer in small quantity through water.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in Poly house conditions at experimental research farm chhapang, Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, District Sirmour, Himachal Pradesh during 2021.

NPK/ha, 150kg NPK/ha and 0kg NPK/ha were used. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with three replications and 16 treatment combinations. The plot size was 1.5m×60cm, and spacing was 30cm×20cm between the rows and plants. The source of fertilizer was polyfeed (19:19:19) which is a water soluble fertilizer.

Results and Discussion

Cost Analysis: These cost analysis elements were computed for the benefit cost ratio, which displays the profit or loss generated by our research.

Total fixed cost: The sum of all the consistent expenses was used to compute the total fixed cost. It is made up of the cost of the poly house risk margin as well as the total fixed cost.

Benefit cost ratio is affected by different parameters which are not changed during the entire season. In all the treatment combinations cost of land was Rs. 50, maintenance cost Rs. 2.50 and fixed cost

52.5 respectively, which is making total of Rs. 800, Rs. 2.50, Rs. 840 of the cost of land, maintenance cost and fixed cost for the entire trial.

Total Variable Cost (Rs.): The total variable cost is made up of a number of different components that are needed during crop cultivation. The cost of Reeva hybrid, Adiva hybrid, Aviva hybrid and Amber hybrid was Rs. 103.7, Rs.95.23, Rs. 152.37 and Rs. 100.52 respectively whereas cost of fertilizers was Rs. 14.88, Rs. 29.76 and 44.65 for F₁, F₂, and F₃. In this research cost of human labor was Rs. 157, cost of electricity Rs. 3, Cost of plant protection Rs. 15, Staking material Rs. 9. These variable's prices fluctuate frequently in repose to market conditions, and they have a substantial impact on a crop's selling price, influencing the benefit-cost ratio. Maximum total variable cost (381.02) is recorded in H₃F₃ (Aviva+150 kg NPK/ha) treatment combination and total variable cost was Rs. 5093.55.

Table 2 Total Variable Cost (Rs.)

Treatment combinations	Cost of Seed (Rs.)	Cost of fertilizer (Rs.)	Cost of human labor (Rs.)	Cost of Electricity (Rs.)	Cost of Plant Protection (Rs.)	Staking material (Rs.)	Total Variable Cost (Rs.)
H ₁ F ₀	103.7	0	157	3	15	9	287.7
H ₁ F ₁	103.7	14.88	157	3	15	9	302.58
H ₁ F ₂	103.7	29.76	157	3	15	9	317.46
H ₁ F ₃	103.7	44.65	157	3	15	9	332.35
H ₂ F ₀	95.23	0	157	3	15	9	279.23
H ₂ F ₁	95.23	14.88	157	3	15	9	294.11
H ₂ F ₂	95.23	29.76	157	3	15	9	308.99
H ₂ F ₃	95.23	44.65	157	3	15	9	323.88
H ₃ F ₀	152.37	0	157	3	15	9	336.37
H ₃ F ₁	152.37	14.88	157	3	15	9	351.25
H ₃ F ₂	152.37	29.76	157	3	15	9	366.13
H ₃ F ₃	152.37	44.65	157	3	15	9	381.02
H ₄ F ₀	100.52	0	157	3	15	9	284.52
H ₄ F ₁	100.52	14.88	157	3	15	9	299.4
H ₄ F ₂	100.52	29.76	157	3	15	9	314.28
H ₄ F ₃	100.52	44.65	157	3	15	9	329.17
Total	1706.76	342.27	2512	48	240	144	5093.55

Table 3 Total cost price and total selling price/m²

Treatment Combinations	Total Cost Price (Rs.)			Total Selling Price (Rs.)		
	Fixed Cost	Variable Cost	Total Cost	Yield (Kg)	Rate /	Total (Rs)
H ₁ F ₀	52.50	287.70	340.20	41.77	40.00	1670.80
H ₁ F ₁	52.50	302.58	355.08	63.56	40.00	2542.40
H ₁ F ₂	52.50	317.46	369.96	100.01	40.00	4000.40
H ₁ F ₃	52.50	332.35	384.85	129.59	40.00	5183.60
H ₂ F ₀	52.50	279.23	331.73	62.52	40.00	2500.80
H ₂ F ₁	52.50	294.11	346.61	77.87	40.00	3114.80
H ₂ F ₂	52.50	308.99	361.49	103.94	40.00	4157.60
H ₂ F ₃	52.50	323.88	376.38	123.25	40.00	4930.00
H ₃ F ₀	52.50	336.37	388.87	75.30	40.00	3012.00
H ₃ F ₁	52.50	351.25	403.75	93.64	40.00	3745.60
H ₃ F ₂	52.50	366.13	418.63	143.15	40.00	5726.00

H₃F₃	52.50	381.02	433.52	199.04	40.00	7961.60
H₄F₀	52.50	284.52	337.02	47.40	40.00	1896.00
H₄F₁	52.50	299.40	351.90	66.10	40.00	2644.00
H₄F₂	52.50	314.28	366.78	79.95	40.00	3198.00
H₄F₃	52.50	329.67	381.78	138.77	40.00	5550.80
Total	840	5093.55	5948.44	1498.46	640	61834.40

Benefit Cost Ratio

The data on benefit cost ratio revealed that maximum benefit (7528.08) was recorded in H₃F₃ (Aviva+150 kg NPK/ha) treatment combination in which maximum cost price is (433.52) recorded in

H₃F₃ (Aviva+150 kg NPK/ha) treatment combination and total selling price is (7961.60) in H₃F₃ (Aviva+150 kg NPK/ha) treatment combination. The maximum (17.37) B:C ratio was recorded by H₃F₃ (Aviva+150 kg NPK/ha) treatment combination.

Table 4 Benefit Cost Ratio

Treatment Combinations	Total Cost Price (Rs.)	Total Selling Price (Rs.)	Benefit	Benefit Cost Ratio
H₁F₀	340.20	1670.80	1330.60	3.91
H₁F₁	355.08	2542.40	2187.32	6.16
H₁F₂	369.96	4000.40	3630.44	9.81
H₁F₃	384.85	5183.60	4798.75	12.47
H₂F₀	331.73	2500.80	2169.07	6.54
H₂F₁	346.61	3114.80	2768.19	7.99
H₂F₂	361.49	4157.60	3796.11	10.50
H₂F₃	376.38	4930.00	4553.62	12.10
H₃F₀	388.87	3012.00	2623.13	6.75
H₃F₁	403.75	3745.60	3341.85	8.28
H₃F₂	418.63	5726.00	5307.37	12.68
H₃F₃	433.52	7961.60	7528.08	17.37
H₄F₀	337.02	1896.00	1558.98	4.63
H₄F₁	351.90	2644.00	2292.10	6.51
H₄F₂	366.78	3198.00	2831.22	7.72
H₄F₃	381.78	5550.80	5169.13	13.54
Total	5948.44	61834.40	55885.96	146.95

Conclusion

Combination, (H₃F₃ Aviva+150kg NPK/ha) was recorded maximum cost price (Rs. 433.52), maximum selling price (Rs.7961.60), benefit (7528.08) and maximum benefit cost ratio 17.37. Hence treatment combination (H₃F₃ Aviva+150kg NPK/ha) gives maximum benefit. It could be due to the better quality of fruits, better shelf life of fruits along with lesser incidence of insect pest and disease in the protected conditions that leads to selling of produce at higher rate ultimately leading to maximum benefit to benefit cost ratio.

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